

A RESEARCH ON QUALITY FACTORS INFLUENCING ONLINE SHOPPING

K. Veerakumar

Assistant Professor in Commerce - BPS, NGM College
(Autonomous), Pollachi, Tamilnadu

Abstract:

There are many reasons why people shop online. For examples, consumers can buy anything at anytime without going to the store; they can find the same product at a lower price by comparing different websites at the same time; they sometime want to avoid pressure when having a face-to-face interaction with salespeople; they can avoid in store traffic jam, etc. These factors can be summarized into four categories-convenience, information, available products and services, and cost and time efficiency.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Convenience & Time Consumption

Introduction:

The internet has played a significant role in our daily life in that people can talk through the internet to one who is actually on the other side of the Earth, can send email around the clock, can search information, can play game with others, and even can buy things online. Meanwhile, Internet shopping has been widely accepted as a way of purchasing products and services it has become a more popular means in the Internet world (Bourlakis et al., 2008). It also provides consumer more information and choices to compare product and price, more choice, convenience, easier to find anything online (Butler and Peppard, 1998). Online shopping has been shown to provide more satisfaction to modern consumers seeking convenience and speed (Yu and Wu, 2007). On the other hand, some consumers still feel uncomfortable to buy online. Lack of trust, for instance, seems to be the major reason that impedes consumers to buy online. Also, consumers may have a need to exam and feel the products and to meet friends and get some more comments about the products before purchasing. Such factors may have negative influence on consumer decision to shop online.

Statement of the Problem:

The marketers have to play a key role in attracting the potential buyers in favor of their products. The buying decision varies as per the information available with the women consumer before buying a particular product. Information available through Internet with the help of cable TV has created a new dimension in making decision before the buying any product. Thus, the decision of buyers depends a lot on the information available with the buyers. All the purchases made by a family follow a certain decision making process.

Objectives of the Study:

The following objectives have been framed to find answer for the above questions raised by the researcher:

- ✓ To study the socio-economic profile of the selected consumers.
- ✓ To examine the factors influencing while purchasing through online.

Methodology:

Data and Sampling:

The data utilized for the study is primary in nature. Primary data have been collected from the sample of 50 consumers in Pollachi Taluk. Convenient sampling is adopted in this study. Simple percentage which is applied to find the factors influencing for online shopping.

Significance of the Study:

This research useful for the consumers who shop online and creates awareness among the consumers about quality factors, time saving, money saving, delivery charges, offers, variety of products, product verification before payment etc. It helps to identify mainly the quality factors involved in online shopping.

Review of Literature:

Hermes (2000) in this study concluded that the consumers not only look for products, but also for online services. Some companies have online customer services available 24 hours. Therefore, even after business hours, customers can ask questions; get necessary support or assistance, which has provided convenience to consumers

Hofacker and Wang et al., (2005) in their study shows that convenient of the internet is one of the impacts on consumers' willingness to buy online (Wang et al., 2005). Online shopping is available for customers around the clock comparing to traditional store as it is open 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

The Tech Faq, (2008) in this study shows that 58 percent chose to shop online because they could shop after-hours, when the traditional stores are closed and 61 percent of the respondents selected to shop online because they want to avoid crowds and wailing lines, especially in holiday shopping.

Profile of Online Consumers:

In Pollachi taluk there are 50 online consumers were taken for this study by adopting convenient sampling method. The demographic factors of online consumers include variables such as age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, type of family, number of members and monthly income. It is presented in table 1.1.

Table 1: Personal Profile

Particulars	Numbers	Percentage
Age		
Up to 20 years	10	20.00
20-30 years	30	60.00
Above 30 years	10	20.00
Gender		
Female	30	60.00
Male	20	40.00
Marital status		
Married	20	40.00
Unmarried	30	60.00
Educational qualification		
Up to School level	10	20.00
Under graduate	30	60.00
Diploma	10	20.00
Occupation		
Student	15	30.00
Employer	20	40.00
Business	15	30.00
Type of family		
Joint family	40	80.00
Nuclear family	10	20.00
Number of members		

Up to 3 members	10	20.00
3-6 members	25	50.00
6 and above	15	30.00
Monthly income (Rs.)		
Up to Rs.15000	10	20.00
Rs.15001 - Rs. 20000	25	50.00
Above Rs. 20000	15	30.00
Factors influencing for Online Shopping		
Convenience	10	20.00
After sales service	5	10.00
open 24 hours a day, 7 days	2	04.00
To avoid crowds and wailing lines	5	10.00
Holiday shopping	8	16.00
Available products and services	5	10.00
Cost and time efficiency	3	06.00
Security	6	12.00
Social contact	6	12.00

Table 5.2 clearly explain that majority of the respondents (60.00%) are belonging to the age group up to 20-30 years, most of the consumers (60.00 %) are female, majority of the consumers (60.00%) are unmarried, most of the consumers (60.00%) are under graduates. Majority of the women consumers (40.00%) are employed in both public and private sector, majority of the consumers (80.00%) are in joint family, most of the consumers (50.00%) family having 3-6 members and majority of the consumers (50.00%) monthly income between Rs.15001 – Rs.20000. Most of the online consumers (30.00%) feels that convenience as the major factor to influence he consumer for online shopping.

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion:

The various findings of the study are given in the following:

- ✓ Majority of the respondents (60.00%) are belonging to the age group up to 20-30 years,
- ✓ Most of the consumers (60.00 %) are female,
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (60.00%) are single,
- ✓ Most of the consumers (60.00%) are under graduates.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (40.00%) are employed in both public and private sector.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (80.00%) are in joint family.
- ✓ Most of the consumers (50.00%) family having 3-6 members and
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (50.00%) monthly income between Rs.15001 – Rs.20000.
- ✓ Most of the women consumers (30.00%) are given problem while purchase only lower quality products.
- ✓ Most of the online consumers (30.00%) feels that convenience as the major factor to influence he consumer for online shopping

Suggestions of the Study:

Based on the findings of the study and the opinion expressed by the women consumers the following suggestions are given:

- ✓ Sellers might consider to offer money-back guarantee policy including shipping expenses refund to reduce purchasing risk.
- ✓ To avoid shipping delay and product lost, , online store may cooperate with other companies with expertise in logistic to improve their distribution channels.
- ✓ Customer service is as important as quality of website.
- ✓ Making web designs and portals novel and sophisticated and web atmospherics friendly is a key to attract visitors.

Conclusion:

Customers more flexible prices and promotions or offering a one-stop shopping service are some more examples that online stores can use to make their business succeed. Online sellers may offer customers to use their bank account number, or stored-value card to complete their purchase. It is also suggested that online stores may offer customer an e-wallet which transfers balance from customer's online bank account to the store payment system. This may help sellers to gain more sales from those who want to buy online products or services but do not have credit card or do not want to use their credit card online.

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